

EIC COMMUNITIES

D1.4 Online EIC portfolio ecosystem database-first version

WP1: A systematic approach to expanding EIC portfolios into EIC deep-tech communities

T1.2: EIC portfolio ecosystem analysis and database

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Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ASTER	Association of Innovative Entrepreneurs in Renewable Technologies
BATT4EU	Batteries for the European Union
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
BSO	Business Support Organization
CAN E	Climate Action Network Europe
CEEI	European Center for Business and Innovation
CENER	National Renewable Energy Technology Experimentation Center
CEO	Chief Executive Officer
CoP	Community of Practice
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic Acid
DTA	Cross-Border Distribution Agreement
DTX	Digital Experience Technology
EACPT	European Association for Clinical Pharmacology and Therapeutics
EARTO	European Association of Research and Technology Organizations
ECCP	European Cluster Collaboration Platform
EDIH	European Digital Innovation Hub
EEN	Enterprise Europe Network
EIC	European Innovation Council
EIP-AHA	European Innovation Partnership on Active and Healthy Ageing
EIT	European Institute of Innovation and Technology
EPO	European Patent Office
ERRIN	European Regions Research and Innovation Network
EuMaT	European Technology Platform for Advanced Materials
EUREC	European Renewable Energy Research Centers
ETIP	European Technology and Innovation Platform

EURADA	European Association of Development Agencies
FEDARENE	European Federation of Agencies and Regions for Energy and the Environment
HoU	Head of Unit
IASP	International Association for the Study of Pain
ICMAB	Institute of Materials Science of Barcelona
IIT	Italian Institute of Technology
INESC TEC	Institute for Systems and Computer Engineering, Technology and Science
INFN	National Institute for Nuclear Physics
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KIC	Knowledge and Innovation Community
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LTD	Limited Company
LDA	Limited Liability Company
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NGI	Next Generation Internet
PM	Programme Manager
PO	Project Officer
RTDI	Research, Technological Development, and Innovation
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
SNET	National Strategy for Energy Transition
SPA	Public Limited Company
SPIRE	Sustainable Process Industry through Resource and Energy Efficiency
SR	Social Responsibility
SRL	Limited Liability Company
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UEHP	European Union of Private Hospitals
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change

1. Introduction

The EIC COMMUNITIES objective is to increase both visibility and impact of the European Innovation Council (EIC)-funded projects by stimulating synergies and innovation breakthroughs. Furthermore, it aims to select, involve, and actively engage key stakeholders who have a vested interest in their activities and results, such as scientific innovators, policy makers, and industry leaders.

The project will create three thematic Communities of Practice (CoPs) in the CleanTech, Industry and Health sectors. Its aim is to co-create diverse online and physical activities, materials and tools that encourage multidisciplinary interactions among EIC projects. Working closely with EIC representatives and EIC Programme Managers (PMs), the project will pioneer new engagement practices and offer policy recommendations for research and innovation in the future of deep tech.

The ultimate goal is to propel future technologies and innovations, driving towards a more connected and innovative future for broad, diverse and gender-inclusive deep tech communities.

This report, named “*Online EIC portfolio ecosystem database-first version*” describes the methodology that will be implemented for the identification and analysis of the EIC projects selected to be part of CoPs as well as their ecosystem of stakeholders. Additionally, it provides the list of EIC projects and stakeholders identified up to this point, while presenting the first results of their analysis. Ultimately, the project aims to systemise this information into two distinct yet strictly connected databases: the **EIC projects' database** and the **stakeholder ecosystem database**.

The information collected will be publicly displayed on [DEEPSYNC](#), the platform powered by EIC COMMUNITIES, thus offering a valuable resource for wider use and engagement within the deep tech landscape. The platform will showcase both the projects chosen to join the CoPs and the associated stakeholder ecosystem.

The initial version of these databases is presented in this deliverable. Subsequent releases, featuring updates on projects and stakeholders identified, will be an ongoing process, with the second release scheduled for June 2024 and the final release in February 2026.

2. Methodology

2.1 Introduction

The EIC COMMUNITIES project unfolds through structured steps to build its databases.

The methodology involves:

1. Surveying EIC PMs to select EIC-funded projects and conducting desk research to evaluate them, analyse their exploitation strategies, and identify needs and challenges for future networking and synergies;
2. Identifying crucial stakeholders with a vested interest in CoPs and subsequently assessing them;
3. Compiling the gathered information into two distinct but closely connected databases that will be reflected on the DEEPSYNC platform.

2.2 Step 1: Selection of thematic and challenge-driven projects

The selection process for the EIC projects involved gathering inputs from PMs and the Project Officer (PO) through two surveys and a co-creation workshop; additional information about the EIC projects was obtained through research conducted on Cordis and data hub platforms.

The initial and follow-up surveys played a pivotal role in gauging their preferences in prioritizing the presence of certain projects, in line with PM's strategic goals. Furthermore, insights gleaned from the co-creation workshop in Brussels, during which each PM described their respective areas of focus, provided valuable context for the selection process and advanced categories of stakeholders that should be included in the CoPs.

The selection aims to engage approximately 145 projects both challenge-driven and thematic projects, with a focus on involving over 15% of actors from widening countries and 35-40% female representatives in the three CoPs.

More information about the selection of projects is available in D1.1 *Needs Assessment and the refinement of portfolio selection*.

2.3 Step 2: Analysis of projects

The project's analysis focuses on key dimensions critical for the effective establishment and management of CoPs. Each set of projects associated with a specific thematic CoP will undergo a preliminary analysis for classification, involving criteria like the thematic area, funding programme, year of funding, etc. This data will be complemented with insights into the exploitation strategies of EIC projects (2.3) and their needs for interdisciplinary exchanges and interactions across portfolios. An online survey, scheduled for completion

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during the February 2024 workshop with EIC projects, will collect this information directly from the EIC beneficiaries.

2.4 Step 3. Analysis of stakeholders

The stakeholder analysis seeks to recognize and engage stakeholders who can contribute to the CoPs. This approach will be organized into three phases:

1. Identification of stakeholders' categories.
2. Development of individual stakeholder profiles.
3. Invitation to project involvement for each profiled stakeholder.

This approach will be supported by a survey to be filled by the EIC COMMUNITIES partners and selected projects.

2.5 Step 4: Creation of the EIC COMMUNITIES project and stakeholder database

The overarching goal is to organize information about selected projects and their stakeholder ecosystem for integration into thematic CoPs. This includes comprehensive details about the projects and their stakeholder ecosystems, encompassing individuals and organizations.

The databases will be accessible on the project platform, DEEPSYNC, from April 2024 and updated every 10 months. Database filters will be defined in the coming months to align with the information needs and interests of website users.

The EIC projects' database aims to systematically organize them under one umbrella, and provide comprehensive information needed for smooth implementation of CoPs' activities and data entry on the DEEPSYNC platform.

The second database aims to identify relevant stakeholders, networks, and initiatives beyond the beneficiaries of portfolio projects who are interested in the EIC projects' results and activities; they can contribute to the CoP activities thus enhancing the overall impact of portfolios and projects.

3. EIC projects' database

3.1 Selection

The selection process for projects to be included in the three CoPs involved a multi-faceted approach, incorporating two surveys and a co-creation workshop with PMs. The initial survey, distributed to all 10 EIC PMs, the PO, and Head of Unit (HoU), aimed to preliminarily assess the needs and challenges of PM portfolios and identify projects for potential focus in the creation of CoPs. We received six replies from the sample of 12 participants, comprising 5 PMs and 1 from the PO. The survey utilized a qualitative approach with open-ended questions.

The subsequent co-creation workshop in Brussels played a crucial role in initiating preparatory activities for establishing CoPs, fostering interaction between the EIC COMMUNITIES consortium, PO, HoU, and PMs. The workshop focused on assessing the daily needs and challenges faced by PMs, reaching agreements on CoP principles and constitution, and identifying external stakeholders for engagement. The primary discussion revolved around validating the three proposed CoPs — **Cleantech, Industry, and Health** — comprising selected projects and relevant stakeholders.

Notably, the challenge emerged in finding a homogeneous group of projects due to the diverse sub-topics within PM portfolios. To address this, a second survey was conducted to gather more insights and validate CoP constitution, supplemented by desk research on Cordis and data hub to complete missing information on the selected projects.

Furthermore, bilateral meetings with the PMs were organized on 11th and 14th December 2023 to finalize the project selection and to explore the objectives for each group and specific expectations towards the CSA project.

The database will be continually updated throughout the project, aligning with the EIC work programme and incorporating contributions from PMs.

3.2 Analysis

The analysis of projects focuses on various dimensions identified as relevant for the smooth set up and management of CoPs. The information analysed included:

- Type of portfolio: Challenge vs Thematic
- Funding Programme
- Thematic area
- Year of funding
- Type of organisation (academic or non-academic)
- Geographical representation

The data was assessed through the existing platforms such as EIC datahub, Cordis, Horizon Results Platform and Innovation Radar, results of the RIBRI project as well as outcomes of discussions with EIC PMs.

The screening process for project objectives, development directions, and milestones is limited due to challenges such as time constraints and difficulties in obtaining information through desk research. However, an essential aspect involves considering the gender of funders and geographical spread for statistical purposes, thus aligning with the project's Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). Information about the numbers women members of the CoPs will be provided in the second version of the database, in June 2024.

The identification of selected projects' exploitation strategies and needs for interdisciplinary exchanges will be facilitated through an online survey during the initial workshop in February (M6). The assessment will further encompass the collection and evaluation of exploitation strategies, the type of expected results and considerations for patenting, taking into account the diverse programs to which these projects have applied, namely, Pathfinder, Accelerator, and Transition. Another important question concerns the identification of the type of external organizations and players that may help the project's beneficiary in exploiting their results. This information will feed the stakeholder database explained in this deliverable in section 5.

Finally, the project will assess the communities' potential for expansion to larger arenas, namely, towards communities involving a larger number of projects continuously expanding even after the end of the EIC COMMUNITIES project.

4. Assessment of the selected projects

The selection and classification of projects for the three CoPs have been meticulously carried out, and the current state-of-the-art of this process is presented in the subsequent sections of this report. The data for each CoP will be presented, providing a comprehensive overview of the projects chosen for the Cleantech, Industry, and Health CoPs. The full list of all the selected projects is available in the Annexes 2-4.

4.1 Cleantech

Starting with the Cleantech CoP, a total of 90 projects have been selected. These projects are distributed across various thematic areas, with 20 focusing on "Novel technologies for resilient agriculture," 38 on "Energy Storage," 4 on "Emerging Clean Tech," 11 on "CO2 | N," and 17 on "Building Materials." The majority of the selected projects received funding in 2022 and 2023 (54 out of 90).

Figure 1: Number of Cleantech beneficiaries per thematic area

Examining the distribution of EIC beneficiaries per funding program, 59 projects applied to the Accelerator, 28 to the Pathfinder, and 3 to the Transition program.

Figure 2: Number of Cleantech beneficiaries per Funding Programme

Finally, hereafter we also show the percentage of Cleantech beneficiaries per country.

Figure 3: Number of Cleantech beneficiaries per country

4.2 Industry

For the Industry thematic area, a total of 47 projects have been selected and classified. Among these, 17 projects fall under the "Awareness & Consciousness (in robotics) through AI" thematic area, 7 under "Enabling Space Technologies," 8 under "Space Debris Sustainability," and 15 under "Sustainable materials & Manufacturing for

Micronanoelectronics." Regarding the year of funding, the majority of selected projects received financial support between 2019 and 2023.

Figure 4: Number of Industry beneficiaries per thematic area

Examining the distribution of EIC beneficiaries across funding programs, 12 projects applied to the Accelerator, 29 to the Pathfinder, and 6 to the Transition program.

Figure 5. Number of Industry beneficiaries per Funding Programme

Additionally, we include a breakdown showing the percentage of beneficiaries per country for a comprehensive understanding of the Industry CoP landscape.

Figure 6: Number Industry of beneficiaries per country

4.3 Health

A total of 66 projects have been selected for the Health thematic area, comprising 8 projects in the "DNA Storage" thematic area and 57 in "Neurotech." The majority of these projects secured funding in 2018 and 2022.

Figure 7: Number of Health beneficiaries per thematic area

Notably, all 66 projects in the Health thematic area are associated with the Pathfinder EIC funding program.

Additionally, we present the overall distribution of beneficiaries per country, highlighting that a significant majority of selected applicants originate from Italy.

Figure 8: Number of Health beneficiaries per country

4.4 The EIC COMMUNITIES portfolio of projects

A total of 203 projects have been selected for the three CoPs. The distribution of these projects in terms of the year of funding indicates that the majority received financial support in 2022 and 2023. Delving into the EIC funding programs, 71 projects applied to the Accelerator, 122 to the Pathfinder, and 9 to the Transition program. The breakdown below aims to provide insights into the diverse geographic representation of the selected projects.

Figure 9: Number of all beneficiaries per country

5. Stakeholders' ecosystem

A stakeholder, in the broadest sense, refers to an individual, group, or entity with a tangible and vested interest or concern in a specific activity, project, organization, or system. These entities may be directly or indirectly connected to the subject matter in question. Stakeholders exhibit diverse network landscapes, and their involvement can take various forms, encompassing both internal and external associations with the entity under consideration. Moreover, the influence and impact wielded by stakeholders can be multifaceted, with degrees of significance that fluctuate based on the circumstances surrounding the endeavour.

In the context of the EIC communities project, stakeholders are entities possessing a keen interest in becoming an integral part of the CoPs. These stakeholders may seek active participation, collaboration, or information exchange within the framework of the EIC communities project, reflecting a shared commitment to its goals and outcomes. In this scenario, stakeholders play a pivotal role in contributing to the success and sustainability of the project by their engagement within the CoPs, thereby fostering a collaborative and synergistic environment conducive to achieving the project's objectives.

To identify and analyse stakeholders a three-step approach is followed, encompassing:

- Stakeholders' identification;
- Stakeholders profiling
- Stakeholders invitation.

The following paragraphs provide concise insights into the methodologies and procedures utilized and planned for each step.

5.1 Stakeholders identification

The analysis of stakeholders starts with the identification of the main categories of stakeholders to be involved. The categories of stakeholders identified give a reference framework, outlining the diverse spectrum of actors whose active engagement is pivotal for the development of the project's activities.

An initial categorization of stakeholders was identified in the proposal, according to each community and their potential relevance to all three communities. This preliminary list was enriched by the contributions of project managers during the co-creation workshop in Brussels. The categories identified are:

- BSO_Incubators
- Universities & research centers _ R&D infrastructures facilities
- Investors
- Corporates
- Start ups & scale ups
- Researchers
- Clinicians
- Architects_Engineers_designers
- Trade associations

- Standardising/Regulatory bodies
- NGO_ Lobbyists & Opinion Leaders

5.2 Stakeholders profiling

For each stakeholder category, single stakeholders will be profiled. At the proposal stage, a list of 92 stakeholder profiles was provided. This list will be expanded by the project’s partners.

The stakeholders identified at the proposal stage are distributed and categorised as follows:

- **Cleantech:** 26 stakeholders have been profiled. This category comprises stakeholders with a direct and vested interest in the environmental and ecological field, and in promoting sustainable practices and eco-friendly initiatives.
- **Industry:** 28 stakeholders have been classified. These entities demonstrate interest and involvement in digital technologies, innovation, and the ever-evolving digital ecosystem. Their engagement can be instrumental in steering the project towards integrating cutting-edge digital solutions and strategies.
- **Health:** 20 stakeholders have been selected. These individuals or entities exhibit a vested interest in health-related initiatives, projects, or outcomes.
- A distinctive group of 14 stakeholders has been identified as **transversal stakeholders**, reflecting a cross-cutting and interdisciplinary nature in their interests and influence. These stakeholders traverse multiple sectors, showcasing a broad and integrated perspective that can contribute synergistically to various facets of the project.

The following table presents the stakeholders identified so far:

Table 1: EIC COMMUNITIES identified stakeholders

CoPs	Stakeholders
<p style="text-align: center;">CleanTech</p>	<p>Actors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Clean Hydrogen Alliance, • Green and Smart Technology Cluster, • DIH4 Climate Neutrality (UNFCCC), • CEEI Aragon, • Tagus Valley, • Verhaert, • CAN E (Climate Action Network Europe), • EERA (European Energy Research Alliance), • EuMaT (European Technology Platform for Advanced Engineering Materials and Technologies), • EUREC (Renewable Energy Research Centers), • Batteries European Partnership Association (BATT4EU), • ETIP Smart Networks for Energy Transition (SNET), • ENEA, • FEDARENE European Federation of Agencies and Regions for Energy and the Environment.

	<p>Initiatives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EPowerEU Plan, • EIC Greenhouse gas programme, • European Cluster Collaboration Platform, • NET4CO2 (PT), • EIT Climate-KIC, • EIT InnoEnergy, • EIT Raw Materials, • EIT Urban Mobility, • SPIRE, • Energy Materials Industrial Research Initiative. <p>Experts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Benjamin Tincq (Marble), • RaquelGarde (CENER), • Rosa Palacín Peiró (ICMAB).
Industry	<p>Actors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cap Digital, • INESC TEC, • SMARTEES Association (SmartEEs FWEA), • EuRobotics, • BDVA-Big Data Value Association, • FIWARE Foundation, • NESSI ETP, • S3 network of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIH), • S3 Platform, • euRobotics, • Digital SME Alliance, • Emilia-Romagna Cluster Network (ASTER), • European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIH), • (Quantun computing) INFN, • IIT, • Politecnico di Torino, • Secpho, • DIGITALbuilt, • Artificial Intelligence & Data Science for Public Administration (AI4PA) - Portugal, <p>Initiatives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital Europe, • Europe's Digital Decade, • ECCP, • DTX Colab, • Digital Transformation Accelerator (DTA), • EIT Digital, • Destination Earth (DestinE), • Next Generation Internet (NGI). <p>Experts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prof. Dr. Paul Lukowicz (Scientific Director of the German Research Center for Artificial Intelligence), • Prof. Fausto Giunchiglia (Computer Science, University of Trento).

<p style="text-align: center;">Health</p>	<p>Actors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HealthCapital - Cluster Healthcare Industries Berlin Brandenburg, • Health Cluster Portugal, • Oslo Cancer Cluster, • Ci3, • WestBIC, • Genopole, • Atlanpole Biotherapies, • European Association for Clinical Pharmacology and Therapeutics (EACPT), • EBRAINS, • European Union of Private Hospitals (UEHP), • Helmholtz Association of German Research Centres, • European Innovation Partnership on Active and Healthy Ageing (EIP-AHA), • Reference Site Collaborative Network.
	<p>Initiatives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EIT Health, • European Health, • Data Space, • EU4Health, CoLAB TRIAL (PT), • Dutch Cancer Society, • European Health Union.
	<p>Experts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dr. Daniela Corda (European Molecular Biology Organization), • Ana Maiques (CEO of neuroscience-based medical device company Neuroelectrics), • Angel Sante (VC on Health), • Fabrizio Conicella (Life Science District).
<p style="text-align: center;">Horizontal</p>	<p>Actors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EARTO, • EPO-European Patent Office, • EURADA-European Association of Development Agencies, • RTDI Innovation School, • Foresight Europe Network.
	<p>Initiatives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2030 Digital Compass, • EIC Women Leadership Programme, • EIC Ecosystem Partnerships, • FundingBox, • EURADA, • ERRIN, • IASP, • EEN.
	<p>Experts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Petra Schaper Rinkel (Senior Researcher at the Center for Innovation Systems & Policy, Austria).

A tailored questionnaire will be developed to further profile the identified stakeholders, and to profile the additional stakeholders that will be included through the project.

The crafted questionnaire will be shared with all the identified projects and with the EIC PMs. This will assure that the projects and the PMs can indicate other stakeholders considered important, that were not yet mapped by the partners. The overall purpose of this questionnaire is to gather a comprehensive array of information from partners and projects regarding potential stakeholders who might express interest in the initiative and becoming part of the CoPs.

The questionnaire will consider:

- General information concerning stakeholder's name, contact information, and geographical location;
- Information concerning core activities: primary activities and sector;
- Specific information concerning activities and features tailored to each stakeholder category;
- Interest in the specific CoPs;
- Number of female/woman-led initiatives. (The goal of EIC communities project is to map and involve the CoPs with at least 50 stakeholders with female leaders.)

All the information gathered in this profiling process will be treated with confidentiality and will remain confined within the consortium. The intention behind collecting this data is to equip the project with the necessary insights to effectively engage with stakeholders, understand their potential interest in the project, and establish meaningful connections.

5.3 Stakeholders' invitation

The project's overarching objective is to map and select a substantial cohort of stakeholders, specifically targeting at least 150 entities, with an average allocation of 50 stakeholders per CoP.

The stakeholders identified in the proposal, including those who will be identified in the next months by the partners, projects, or PMs, will undergo the selection process facilitated by the information collected in the questionnaire.

Every profiled stakeholder will be contacted. The project partners will establish contact by sending the invitation letter to the stakeholders identified during the proposal stage and in the subsequent months. Each partner holds direct responsibility for reaching out to stakeholders based on prior collaborations, personal connections, shared network memberships, etc. Partners will invite the profiled stakeholders to join the CoPs and become members of the EIC COMMUNITIES' stakeholder database. Integration into the database will only proceed if the stakeholders express a willingness to be included, respect their autonomy, and ensure active engagement. This approach ensures that the database is a living and active resource.

5.4 Next Steps

Once the target of at least 150 stakeholders profiled and invited has been reached, stakeholders will be engaged in the development of the CoPs and will feed into the Stakeholder Database. At M10, D1.5 - Online EIC portfolio ecosystem database -second version will be released, and the results of these activities will be presented.

Figure 10: Stakeholders' ecosystem process

6. Potential for expansion

The EIC COMMUNITIES project pursues the expansion of its CoPs. This involves a systematic examination of the growth trajectories delineated in the exploitation roadmaps for both the overarching communities and the projects within them. These roadmaps serve as comprehensive frameworks, highlighting the different requirements, strategic orientations, and anticipated developmental pathways that underpin the evolution of the projects within the broader CoP context.

The project seeks to gain effective insights into the developmental landscapes of the communities and projects it oversees. The exploitation roadmaps provide a forward-looking perspective, outlining the objectives shaping the trajectory of each community's and project's progression.

The analysis of exploitation roadmaps extends to the individual projects encapsulated within the CoPs. Each project, being a distinct entity with its own set of objectives and results, will be subject to analysis for its exploitation roadmap. This analytical process aims to discern resource requirements, strategic imperatives, and critical milestones that characterize the project's growth and evolution within the overarching CoP framework.

To reach this end, the following methodological steps will be followed:

- 1- **Identification of KERs (Key Exploitable Results):** what are the main innovations that the projects develop?
- 2- **Identification of exploitation strategies:** what are the foreseen strategies for the main KERs in the projects?
- 3- **Requirements assessment:** based on the exploitation strategies identified, what are the main aspects that need to be addressed to guarantee the expansion of CoPs?

The following paragraphs give an overview of the methodologies and process employed for each step.

6.1 Identification of KERs

KERs identification is key for comprehending the type of strategic planning essential for achieving expansion. Through the analysis of the various types of results, it is possible to gain insights concerning the specific outcomes needing emphasis, amplification, or broader dissemination.

6.2 Assessment of exploitation roadmaps

Following the identification of the main projects' KERs, the subsequent phase involves assessing the main exploitation strategies. This critical step enables the delineation of a comprehensive framework within which the identified results will be developed and exploited. These strategies not only provide a roadmap for the practical implementation of the results but also contribute to the overarching vision of how these outcomes will be strategically utilized and leveraged for maximum impact.

6.3 Requirements assessment

The identification of KERs and the formulation of exploitation strategies facilitate the determination of requirements necessary for the maximization of projects' results. The outcomes of this analysis, when integrated, will contribute into the final DEEPSYNC platform. This means that by highlighting exploitation roadmaps, a clearer understanding emerges regarding the attributes and areas requiring attention to enhance innovation and amplify the impacts of chosen projects. Consequently, the results of such analysis serve as essential filters guiding the implementation and utilization of the ultimate DEEPSYNC platform, steering its deployment towards maximizing innovation and impact across these selected projects.

6.4 Exploitation survey

To carry out this analysis a survey has been designed and will be presented to EIC beneficiaries during the workshop scheduled for February 2024- M6, organized by EurA. This survey is specifically designed for project coordinators and comprises four targeted questions centred around the theme of project exploitation. The survey can be assessed in Annex 1.

7. Conclusions

This report *D1.4 Online EIC portfolio ecosystem database – first version* outlined the EIC COMMUNITIES' adopted methodology for the selection and assessment of EIC selected projects and their ecosystem of stakeholders. This report also provides the up-to-date list of projects and stakeholders identified so far by the project partners as well as a preliminary analysis.

The project methodology includes surveying EIC PMs to select EIC-funded projects and conducting desk research to analyse them. Additionally, it involves identifying crucial stakeholders with a vested interest in CoPs and subsequently assessing them.

The significance of this report lies in its potential to define pathways for expansion to larger communities, provide insights into EIC projects' exploitation strategies, and identify their needs for interdisciplinary exchanges and interactions within and across communities. The information described in this document will set the ground for partners to build strategic and tailored activities that spur synergies between projects and the thematic communities; their collaborations and matchmaking with key stakeholders; EIC beneficiaries' anchoring to CoPs and active participation; potential expansion as part of the post-project sustainability plan; networking activities and synergies building within the three communities.

At present, a total of 203 projects have been selected for the three CoPs, with a breakdown of 90 projects for the Cleantech CoP, 47 for the Industry CoP and 66 for the Health CoP. Out of these, 71 projects applied to the Accelerator, 122 to the Pathfinder, and 9 to the Transition program.

The project identified 92 stakeholder profiles – stemming from the project proposal. Partners will expand this list, in collaboration with the EIC PMs, and contact each stakeholder. Stakeholders are categorized into Cleantech (26 profiles), Industry (28 profiles), and Health (20 profiles). Additionally, a distinctive group of 14 stakeholders with a transversal and interdisciplinary nature has been identified. These stakeholders span multiple sectors, offering a broad and integrated perspective to contribute synergistically to various facets of the project.

The gathered information will be openly presented on the DEEPSYNC platform, providing a valuable resource for broader utilization and involvement within the deep tech landscape. The platform will feature both the selected projects joining the CoPs and the corresponding stakeholder ecosystem.

The next 2 releases at M10 and M30 will provide updates on the selection process and analysis.

8. ANNEXES

Annex 1 – Exploitation survey

Table 2: Exploitation survey

QUESTIONS	ANSWERS
In your project, what are the main types of results? Choose up to three options from the list below:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hardware technology • Software and Algorithms • Methodology • Model • Process • Advancement in knowledge • Service • Database • Formula • Standard • Other (please specify)
Have you submitted or considered a patent to protect your results?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
What are the strategies for exploiting the main results of the project after its ends? Please choose up to three options from the following	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academic exploitation (e.g., publications, new courses, etc.) • Creation of a new standard/Development of new policies • Direct commercialization of a new product or service • Knowledge transfer • Licensing/transfer of IPR • New application/use case of an existing product or service • Research and scientific exploitation • Spin- off, joint venture or startup launch • TRL Upscaling through further research • Replication of the concept (in other geographical areas or sites)
Considering the option selected in the previous question, which external organizations and players may help the project's partner in exploiting the results? Choose up to five options from the following	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community organizations • International organizations • Media companies • Non-governmental organizations • Other educational organizations • Philanthropic foundations • Potential commercial partners (customer) • Potential commercial partners (suppliers)

- Private funders
- Professional associations
- Public funders
- Regulatory bodies
- Research organizations
- Technical experts
- Universities and other educational institutions

Annex 2 – Cleantech EIC projects

Programme	Thematic / Challenges	Organisation Name (Coordinator if applicable)	Project Acronym	Country	Thematic Area
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	SUNTHERM APS	SmartHeat	Denmark	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	NORRHYDRO OY	Norrdigi	Finland	Energy Storage
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	UNIVERSITE DE LIEGE	MOAMMM	Belgium	Building Materials
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	TERALOOP OY	Teraloop EES	Finland	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	FOCALSPEC OY	FOCALSPEC	Finland	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	LANCEY ENERGY STORAGE	Solar QUEST	France	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	ECO-TECH CERAM	EcoStock	France	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	NANOMAKERS	DEBIMAX	France	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	KAYRROS	PAWES	France	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	LIPOFABRIK	Lipofabrik	France	Novel technologies for resilient agriculture
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI TRENTO	BOHEME	Italy	Building Materials
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	ENERGYNEST AS	HEAT2VALUE	Norway	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	CHARGE2C-NEWCAP LDA	HYCAP	Portugal	Energy Storage
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	BCAM - BASQUE CENTER FOR APPLIED MATHEMATICS	ADAM^2	Spain	Building Materials
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	MILLOR ENERGY SOLUTIONS SL	BATTERY PLUS	Spain	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	CRI EHF	Circlenergy	Switzerland	Emerging Clean Tech

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EIC Accelerator	Thematic	LEYDENJAR TECHNOLOGIES BV	LeydenJar	The Netherlands	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	AVILOO GMBH	AVILOO bcheck	Austria	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	SOLAR ENERGY CONVERSION POWER CORPORATION	Powerbox	Belgium	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	CEMGREEN APS	CemShale + CemTower	Denmark	Building Materials
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	PULSEDEON OY	Coldab	Finland	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	WATTALPS	WATTELSE	France	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	Electrochaea GmbH	Echaea	Germany	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	SKELETON TECHNOLOGIES GMBH	X-CAP	Germany	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	NANOM EHF	Nano-Edison	Iceland	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	Criaterra Innovation LTD	RE-CREATE	Israel	Building Materials
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	ADDIONICS IL LTD	Addionics	Israel	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	ONIO AS	WISE	Norway	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	ENERPOLY AB	ENERZ	Sweden	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Challenge	DEEP BRANCH BIOTECHNOLOGY LTD	Proton	United Kingdom	CO2 N
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	LIMATECH	ORION PROJECT	France	Energy Storage
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN	ECOLOPES	Germany	Building Materials
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	INERATEC GMBH	IMPOWER2X	Germany	Emerging Clean Tech
EIC Transition	Thematic	ECONCRETE TECH LTD	Living Ports	Israel	Building Materials
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	Fibritech SP Zoo	Fibritech	Poland	Building Materials

EIC Accelerator	Thematic	Sveltedca Partners SRL	Svelte	Romania	Building Materials
EIC Accelerator	Challenge	AGROBIOGEL GMBH	Agrobiogiel	Austria	Novel technologies for resilient agriculture
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	LITHOS CROP PROTECT GMBH	Micro Dispensers for sustainable plant protection	Austria	Novel technologies for resilient agriculture
EIC Accelerator	Challenge	OCTAVE	iBEMS-SeLiBat	Belgium	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Challenge	LEKATECH OY	RHINO	Finland	Building Materials
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	CARBO CULTURE OY	CARBONCAPS	Finland	Emerging Clean Tech
EIC Accelerator	Challenge	BROADBIT BATTERIES OY	SodiScale	Finland	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Challenge	RISUTEC OY	Forest Maker	Finland	Novel technologies for resilient agriculture
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	Matterup	Clayment	France	Building Materials
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	COLD PAD	C_CLAW_C_HAWK	France	Building Materials
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	DREAM	France	Novel technologies for resilient agriculture
EIC Accelerator	Challenge	SABI AGRI	SWARM	France	Novel technologies for resilient agriculture
EIC Accelerator	Challenge	Green Spot Technologies	FI'Our Planet	France	Novel technologies for resilient agriculture
EIC Accelerator	Challenge	TWAICE TECHNOLOGIES GMBH	Predictive Battery Analytics	Germany	Energy Storage
EIC Transition	Thematic	ECHEMICLES ZARTKORUEN	SolarCO2Value	Hungary	Emerging Clean Tech

		MUKODO RESZVENYTARSASAG			
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	Treble	Treble	Iceland	Building Materials
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	TECHNION - ISRAEL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY	SafeWax	Israel	Novel technologies for resilient agriculture
EIC Accelerator	Challenge	FREEZEM CRYOGENICS LTD	FreezeM	Israel	Novel technologies for resilient agriculture
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	ACCADEMIA EUROPEA DI BOLZANO	ZERAF	Italy	Building Materials
EIC Accelerator	Challenge	DIGIFARM AS	CropCloud	Norway	Novel technologies for resilient agriculture
EIC Accelerator	Challenge	ARBOREABIOFOODS LDA	Biosolar Leaf	Portugal	Novel technologies for resilient agriculture
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS	DARKWIN	Spain	Novel technologies for resilient agriculture
EIC Accelerator	Challenge	SYMPOWER BV	Flex4Scale	The Netherlands	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Challenge	AQUABATTERY BV	AquaBattery	The Netherlands	Energy Storage
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	DET KONGELIGE DANSKE KUNST- AKADEMISSKOLER FOR ARKITEKTIR, DESIGN OG KONSERVERING	Fungaterrria	Denmark	Building Materials
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET GRAZ	VanillaFlow	Austria	Energy Storage
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	Katolische University of Leuven (KU Leuven)	Mi-Hy	Belgium	CO2 N

EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	UNIVERSITE DE NAMUR ASBL	BABOTS	Belgium	Novel technologies for resilient agriculture
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	CESKE VYSOKE UCENI TECHNICKE V PRAZE	SENSORBEES	Czechia	Novel technologies for resilient agriculture
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	AARHUS UNIVERSITET	AELECTRA	Denmark	Energy Storage
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	Solar Foods OY	HYDROCOW	Finland	CO2 N
EIC Accelerator	Challenge	EASYL ZINC	SUPERZINC	France	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	ELICIT PLANT	Generation Biosourced Biologicals	France	Novel technologies for resilient agriculture
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	Technical University of Munchen (TUM)	ECOMO	Germany	CO2 N
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	DEUTSCHES ZENTRUM FUR LUFT - UND RAUMFAHRT EV	SULPHURREAL	Germany	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	COMPUTOMICS GMBH	TRAIT4.0	Germany	Novel technologies for resilient agriculture
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	YNERGEIES STIN EPISTIMI KAI TECHNOLOGIA-SYNEST IDIOTIKI KEFALAIOUCHIKI ETAIREIA	HiCon	Greece	CO2 N
EIC Transition	Thematic	THE PROVOST, FELLOWS, FOUNDATION SCHOLARS & THE OTHER MEMBERS OF BOARD, OF THE COLLEGE OF THE HOLY & UNDIVIDED TRINITY OF QUEEN ELIZABETH NEAR DUBLIN	AirInMotion	Ireland	CO2 N

EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	Consiglio Nazionale Ricerche Istituto Tecnologie Membrane (CNR-ITM)	DAM4CO2	Italy	CO2 N
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	POLITECNICO DI MILANO	M-TES	Italy	Energy Storage
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	ACCADEMIA EUROPEA DI BOLZANO	Muspell	Italy	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	XFARM TECHNOLOGIES ITALIA SRL	xTrap	Italy	Novel technologies for resilient agriculture
EIC Accelerator	Challenge	ENERGY DOME SPA	CO2 Battery	Italy	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	GBM Works B.V.	SIMPLE	The Netherlands	Building Materials
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	SINTEF ENERGI AS	ReZilient	Norway	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	Flexofibres Europa SL	Flexofibers	Spain	Building Materials
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	UNIVERSIDAD AUTONOMA DE BARCELONA (UAB)	CONFETI	Spain	CO2 N
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	FUNDACIO INSTITUT DE CIENCIES FOTONIQUES (ICFO)	ICONIC	Spain	CO2 N
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	FUNDACIO PRIVADA INSTITUT CATALA D'INVESTIGACIO (ICIQ)	SUPERVAL	Spain	CO2 N
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	RIEGO SUR SA	PUSH-CCC	Spain	Energy Storage
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	CIC Energy GUNE	HIPERZAB	Spain	Energy Storage
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	POLYFLY SL	HoverPollination	Spain	Novel technologies for resilient agriculture
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	LUNDS UNIVERSITET	MINICOR	Sweden	CO2 N
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	ODD.BOT BV	Agri-Think Robot	The Netherlands	Novel technologies for resilient agriculture

EIC Accelerator	Thematic	SAIA AGROBOTICS BV	AUTOFARM	The Netherlands	Novel technologies for resilient agriculture
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Annex 3 – Industry EIC projects

Programme	Thematic / Challenges	Organisation Name (Coordinator if applicable)	Project Acronym	Country	Thematic Area
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	UNIVERSITEIT ANTWERPEN	PRINGLE	Belgium	Sustainable materials & Manufacturing for Micronanoelectronics
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	UNIVERSITEIT GENT	CSOC	Belgium	Sustainable materials & Manufacturing for Micronanoelectronics
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	UNIVERSITE CATHOLIQUE DE LOUVAIN	FITNESS	Belgium	Sustainable materials & Manufacturing for Micronanoelectronics
EIC Accelerator	Challenge	ARCSEC	DeDust	Belgium	Space Debris Sustainability
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	Veoware	SATAGILITY-GO2MARKET	Belgium	Enabling Space Technologies
EIC Transition	Thematic	Zabio	Zabio	Denmark	Sustainable materials & Manufacturing for Micronanoelectronics
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET	SiComb	Denmark	Sustainable materials & Manufacturing for Micronanoelectronics
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	AALTO KORKEAKOULUSAATIO SR	SCOLED	Finland	Sustainable materials & Manufacturing for Micronanoelectronics
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	AURORA PROPULSION TECHNOLOGIES OY	Aurora Plasma Brake (APB)	Finland	Space Debris Sustainability

EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	Aalto University	SUSTAIN	Finland	Awareness & Consciousness (in robotics) through AI
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	ENERSENS	EN.MOTION	France	Sustainable materials & Manufacturing for Micronanoelectronics
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	UNIVERSITE DE BORDEAUX	FVLLMONTI	France	Sustainable materials & Manufacturing for Micronanoelectronics
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	UNIVERSITE PARIS-SACLAY	BAYFLEX	France	Sustainable materials & Manufacturing for Micronanoelectronics
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	Share My Space	CASSIOPEE	France	Space Debris Sustainability
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	Infinite Orbits	Endurance	France	Space Debris Sustainability
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	University of Bordeaux	RadioSpin	France	Awareness & Consciousness (in robotics) through AI
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	OLEDCOMM	SATELIFE	France	Enabling Space Technologies
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	Greenwave	Greenwave	France	Enabling Space Technologies
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	GESELLSCHAFT FUR ANGEWANDTE MIKRO UND OPTOELEKTRONIK MIT BESCHRANKTERHAFTUNG AMO GMBH	POSEIDON	Germany	Sustainable materials & Manufacturing for Micronanoelectronics
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET DRESDEN	PROGENY	Germany	Sustainable materials & Manufacturing for Micronanoelectronics
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT LEUVEN	MEESSST	Germany	Enabling Space Technologies
EIC Transition	Thematic	University of Stuttgart	SUPREME	Germany	Enabling Space Technologies

EIC Accelerator	Challenge	Energy Robotics	edge air	Germany	Awareness & Consciousness (in robotics) through AI
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	UNIVERSITAET BREMEN	MUHAI	Germany	Awareness & Consciousness (in robotics) through AI
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	Max Planck Institute for Software Systems	SymAware	Germany	Awareness & Consciousness (in robotics) through AI
EIC Transition	Thematic	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAT DARMSTADT	VRP	Germany	Awareness & Consciousness (in robotics) through AI
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	FONDAZIONE ISTITUTO ITALIANO DI TECNOLOGIA	5D NanoPrinting	Italy	Sustainable materials & Manufacturing for Micronanoelectronics
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	FONDAZIONE ISTITUTO ITALIANO DI TECNOLOGIA	3D-BRICKS	Italy	Sustainable materials & Manufacturing for Micronanoelectronics
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA	MAIA	Italy	Awareness & Consciousness (in robotics) through AI
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	University of Pisa	EMERGE	Italy	Awareness & Consciousness (in robotics) through AI
EIC Transition	Thematic	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI VERONA	ROBIOPSY	Italy	Awareness & Consciousness (in robotics) through AI
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	Politecnico Di Milano	IPROP	Italy	Enabling Space Technologies

EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	University of Luxembourg	SYMBIOTIK	Luxembourg	Awareness & Consciousness (in robotics) through AI
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	STICHTING RADBOUD UNIVERSITEIT	CAVAA	The Netherlands	Awareness & Consciousness (in robotics) through AI
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	UNIVERSITETET I BERGEN	Nanolace	Norway	Sustainable materials & Manufacturing for Micronanoelectronics
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	FUNDACIO EURECAT	GuestXR	Spain	Awareness & Consciousness (in robotics) through AI
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTÍFICAS	VALAWAI	Spain	Awareness & Consciousness (in robotics) through AI
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	Universidad Politecnica de Madrid	METATOOL	Spain	Awareness & Consciousness (in robotics) through AI
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID	ASTOUND	Spain	Awareness & Consciousness (in robotics) through AI
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	UNIVERSIDAD CARLOS III DE MADRID	E.T.Pack	Spain	Space Debris Sustainability
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	SENER AEROESPACIAL SOCIEDAD ANONIMA	BMOM	Spain	Space Debris Sustainability
EIC Transition	Thematic	UNIVERSIDAD CARLOS III DE MADRID	E.T.PACK-F	Spain	Space Debris Sustainability

EIC Transition	Thematic	Plantics HoldingBV	SWOP	The Netherlands	Sustainable materials & Manufacturing for Micronanoelectronics
EIC Accelerator	Thematic	Dawn Aerospace	DETOX	The Netherlands	Enabling Space Technologies
EIC Accelerator	Challenge	Lumi Space	Lumi SLR	United Kingdom	Space Debris Sustainability
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	OXFORD BROOKES UNIVERSITY	E-pi	United Kingdom	Awareness & Consciousness (in robotics) through AI
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	ASTON UNIVERSITY	NEU-ChiP	United Kingdom	Awareness & Consciousness (in robotics) through AI

Annex 4 – Health EIC projects

Programme	Thematic / Challenges	Organisation Name (Coordinator if applicable)	Project Acronym	Country	Thematic Area
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	CONSORCI INSTITUT D'INVESTIGACIONS BIOMEDIQUES AUGUST PI I SUNYER	4-DBR	Spain	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	GEORG-AUGUST-UNIVERSITAT GOTTINGEN STIFTUNG OFFENTLICHEN RECHTS	ADOPD	Germany	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	HADASSAH MEDICAL ORGANIZATION	AlternativesToGd	Israel	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	COMMISSARIAT A L ENERGIE ATOMIQUE ET	AROMA	France	Neurotech

		AUX ENERGIES ALTERNATIVES			
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	UPPSALA UNIVERSITET	B-CRATOS	Sweden	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	SERVICIO CANARIO DE LA SALUD	BionicVEST	Spain	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	FUNDACIO INSTITUT CATALA DE NANOCIENCIA I NANOTECNOLOGIA	BrainCom	Spain	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	AALTO KORKEAKOULUSAATIO SR	BREAKBEN	Finland	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	FUNDACION IMDEA NANOCIENCIA	ByAxon	Spain	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	POLITECNICO DI TORINO	CEREBRO	Italy	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	MEDIZINISCHE UNIVERSITAET WIEN	CITRUS	Austria	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT EINDHOVEN	CONNECT	The Netherlands	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	UNIVERSITY OF BATH	CResPace	United Kingdom	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI ROMA TOR VERGATA	CROSSBRAIN	Italy	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	IDRYMA TECHNOLOGIAS KAI EREVNAS	DynAMic	Greece	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	HAUTE ECOLE SPECIALISEE DE SUISSE OCCIDENTALE	GAMMA-MRI	Switzerland	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	UNIVERSITY OF CYPRUS	GLADIATOR	Cyprus	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	INSTITUT PASTEUR	HearLight	France	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	FONDAZIONE ISTITUTO ITALIANO DI TECNOLOGIA	HERMES	Italy	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI FIRENZE	HYPERPROBE	Italy	Neurotech

EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT LEUVEN	HYPERSTIM	Belgium	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	FONDAZIONE ISTITUTO ITALIANO DI TECNOLOGIA	HyVIS	Italy	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	SCUOLA INTERNAZIONALE SUPERIORE DI STUDI AVANZATI DI TRIESTE	IN-FET	Italy	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	UNIVERSITAIR MEDISCH CENTRUM UTRECHT	INTRECOM	The Netherlands	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder		STARLAB BARCELONA SL	LUMINOUS	Spain	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA SANTE ET DE LA RECHERCHE MEDICALE	MICROVASC	France	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	FUNDACIO INSTITUT CATALA DE NANOCIENCIA I NANOTECNOLOGIA	MINIGRAPH	Spain	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	INSTITUTO DE MEDICINA MOLECULAR JOAO LOBO ANTUNES	MyoChip	Portugal	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	FONDAZIONE ISTITUTO ITALIANO DI TECNOLOGIA	NanoBRIGHT	Italy	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI PAVIA	NECTAR	Italy	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	COMMISSARIAT A L ENERGIE ATOMIQUE ET AUX ENERGIES ALTERNATIVES	NEMO BMI	France	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	ASTON UNIVERSITY	NEU-ChiP	United Kingdom	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	SCUOLA SUPERIORE DI STUDI UNIVERSITARI E DI PERFEZIONAMENTO S ANNA	NeuHeart	Italy	Neurotech

EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	THE UNIVERSITY OF BIRMINGHAM	NEURAM	United Kingdom	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	UNIVERSITAT ZURICH	NeuraViPeR	Switzerland	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	IDRYMA TECHNOLOGIAS KAI EREVNAS	NEUREKA	Greece	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	SERVICIO DE SALUD DE CASTILLA LA MANCHA	Neurofibres	Spain	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	ASTON UNIVERSITY	NEUROPA	United Kingdom	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	UNIVERSIDADE DE AVEIRO	NeuroStimSpinal	Portugal	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	NEUROELECTRICS BARCELONA SL	Neurotwin	Spain	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	ALBERT-LUDWIGS-UNIVERSITAET FREIBURG	NIMA	Germany	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET	OpenMIND	Denmark	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	OXiNEMS	Italy	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI FIRENZE	PATHOS	Italy	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	LUNDS UNIVERSITET	ph-coding	Sweden	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	GEORG-AUGUST-UNIVERSITAT GOTTINGEN STIFTUNG OFFENTLICHEN RECHTS	Plan4Act	Germany	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	AGENZIA NAZIONALE PER LE NUOVE TECNOLOGIE, L'ENERGIA E LO SVILUPPO ECONOMICO SOSTENIBILE	RISEUP	Italy	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	Rose	France	Neurotech

EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	SensApp	Italy	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	UNIVERSITA CAMPUS BIO MEDICO DI ROMA	SOMA	Italy	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	AARHUS UNIVERSITET	SpinAge	Denmark	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	AARHUS UNIVERSITET	STARDUST	Denmark	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI PADOVA	SYNCH	Italy	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	UNIVERSITY OF SOUTHAMPTON	TISuMR	United Kingdom	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON	TOUCHLESS	United Kingdom	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Thematic	FONDAZIONE ISTITUTO ITALIANO DI TECNOLOGIA	TOX-Free	Italy	Neurotech
EIC Pathfinder	Challenge	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT	UPSIDE	The Netherlands	Neurotech

